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FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT (FDI) AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIA'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Foreign investment is a strategic instrument of development policy. It plays an important role in the long-term economic development of a country by augmenting availability of capital, enhancing competitiveness of the domestic economy through transfer of technology, strengthening infrastructure, raising productivity, generating new employment opportunities and boosting exports. In the wake of economic liberalization policy initiated in 1991, the Government of India has undertaken several measures to encourage foreign investment, both direct and portfolio, in almost all sectors of the economy. However, the emphasis has been on the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows in the development of infrastructure, technological upgradation of industry and setting up of Special Economic Zones (SEZs). With a vast reservoir of skilled and cost-effective manpower, India is now recognized as one of the most attractive investment destinations by reputed international rating organizations. This paper made an analysis to review the trends of foreign direct investments in Indian economy, particularly after a decade of economic reforms and analyze the impact on the economic development of the country.

Keywords: *Foreign Direct Investment, Economy, Gross Domestic Product, Exports, and Foreign Exchange Reserves.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) aims to attain financial stability and economic growth with the help of investments in different sectors. After liberalization of trade policies in India, there has been a positive Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate in Indian economy. Foreign Direct Investments help in developing the economy by generating employment to the unemployed, generating revenues in the form of tax and incomes, financial stability to the government, development of infrastructure, backward and forward linkages to the domestic firms for the requirements of raw materials, tools, business infrastructure, and act as support for the financial system. There are many businesses and individuals who would earn their livelihood through the foreign investments. Foreign technology induction could be encouraged through FDI and through foreign technology collaboration agreements.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

In case of foreign direct investment (FDI), the private foreign investor either sets up a branch or a subsidiary in the recipient country. The private foreign investors exercise almost complete control over the assets created by them in the developing countries in which private foreign capital has been invested. Capital is the engine of economic development and this statement is gaining importance in the recent times. Traditionally, the various sources of capital for developing countries were either the demand for their output from industrial countries or foreign aid, or loan from foreign banks. In today's scenario, where official development assistance flows are steadily declining, high bank interest rates and portfolio investment involve risks. Foreign direct investment is considered to be a major source of funds which may contribute in increasing the economic growth rate of the developing countries. Recently the governments' liberal and open policy reform in foreign direct investment (FDI) aims to integrate the Indian economy with this world economy. Foreign direct investment (FDI) helps to overtake the problem of low capital, low growth rate, untapped natural and human resources,

high rate of inflation, unemployment, balance of payment and other structural and administrative rigidities. Its ability to deal with the major obstacles, namely shortages of financial resources and technology and skills, has made of the centre of attention to developing countries. It is the reason most of the countries, especially developing countries like India are battling for attracting more and more foreign direct investment (FDI). Hence, this study is pertinent to analyze the impact of FDI inflows in the economic development of India.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In order to realize the significance of foreign direct investment in the Indian economy, the following objectives have been set.

- 1) To analyze the trends of Foreign Direct Investment over the period of study;
- 2) To assess the impact of the FDI in the economic development of India;
- 3) To offer valuable suggestions for the enhancement of the FDI for the attainment of an economic growth of a country.

IV. SURVEY OF EXISTING LITERATURE

A significant amount of research has been done on the working and performance of FDI in India, by academicians and researchers. The literature obtained by investigators, in the form of the research studies, articles of researchers, is briefly reviewed in this part.

Salisu A. Afees (2004) examined the determinants and impact of Foreign Direct Investment on economic Growth in Developing Countries using Nigeria as a case study. The study observed that inflation, debt burden, and exchange rate significantly influence FDI flows into Nigeria.

Marc Lombard, Annick Lombard (2011) suggested that foreign direct investment (FDI) has had a significant positive bearing on the Chinese economy and a considerably more moderate effect on that of India. This discrepancy is attributed, in particular, to the composition and nature of FDI, and the institutional framework within which FDI is received.

Shalini Aggarwal et.al., (2012) in their study analyzed the sector-wise and year-wise Foreign Direct Investment inflows in India. Services sector is the favourite sector with highest FDI inflow 20%. Telecommunication and Computer hardware & software is the next favourite sector with 8% and 7%.

Pankaj Chaudhary (2013) highlighted in their study that FDI inflows have shown significant growth after the economic reforms of 1991 particularly in the service sector. The service sector has a major contribution to country's Gross Domestic Product and its increasing rapidly. There has a sharp increase in the service sector share of GDP. FDI can play catalytic role in a growing economy like India.

Abhishek Parikh and Harshika Gobbad (2014) in their paper studied the determinants of FDI in services and the growth of GDP and FDI inflows from the year 2000-01 to the year 2011-12. The study revealed that India has witnessed healthy inflow of foreign investment since 2001 and this has helped the country to build a healthy foreign exchange reserve for its country and control its trade deficit.

Malla Reddy (2014) observed in his paper that the service sector is one of the dominating sectors in attracting more FDI Inflows and India is considered to be the third most preferred investment destination in the world after China and United States.

V. METHODOLOGY

This part deals with the description of methodology and the steps undertaken for collection and analysis of data and presenting the findings of the investigation. The study is carried out to analyze and explore the inflow of Foreign Direct Investments in India and its impact on Indian Economy.

Nature and Sources of Data

The present study is of analytical nature and makes use of secondary data. The relevant secondary data are collected from the following sources: Publications of Reserve Bank of India, Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy, (RBI Various Issues), Economic Surveys of Government of India (Various Issues),

Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIIP), Central Statistical Organization (CSO) and various FDI related journals have also been referred to.

Tools Used for Analysis

The analysis of the data forms the core part of the research. In order to analyze the data and draw conclusions, various statistical tools like growth rates and correlation have been used through EXCEL and SPSS Software.

Period of the Study

The study period was ten years, starting from the year 2005-06 to 2015-16.

Limitations of the Study

- i. As this study is mainly based on secondary data as published in various publications of the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and other reports. These data are based on the historical accounting concept, which ignores the impact of inflation.
- ii. The horizon of the study is merely confined to a less number of variables as the measuring inflow of Foreign Direct Investment and its impact on the Economic development.

VI. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

1. Inflow of Foreign Direct Investment Equity Inflows and Exports

FDI equity inflows comprising equity in branches, all share in subsidiaries and associates (except non-participating, preferred shares that are treated as debt securities and are included under other direct investment capital) and other capital contributions such as provisions of machinery, etc. The year-wise amount of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Equity Inflows secured by the country along with the amounts of exports is furnished in Table 1.

TABLE 1
YEAR-WISE AMOUNTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT (FDI) EQUITY INFLOWS AND EXPORTS IN INDIA

Years	FDI Equity Inflows (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (In %)	Exports (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (In %)
2006-07	56,390	-	5,71,779	-
2007-08	98,642	74.93	6,55,864	14.71
2008-09	1,42,829	44.80	8,40,755	28.19
2009-10	1,23,120	-13.80	8,45,534	0.57
2010-11	97,320	-20.96	11,42,922	35.17
2011-12	1,65,146	69.69	14,65,959	28.26
2012-13	1,21,907	-26.18	16,34,318	11.48
2013-14	1,47,518	21.01	19,05,011	16.56
2014-15	1,89,107	28.19	18,96,445	-0.45
2015-16	2,62,322	38.72	17,16,378	-9.49
CAGR (%)	-	16.62	-	11.62

Source: Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion & Reserve Bank of India.

Table 1 exhibit the growth rate of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Equity Inflows during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The total amount of FDI Equity Inflows has increased from ₹ 56,390 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 1,42,829 crores in 2008-09. Even though the amount of FDI equity inflows declined to ₹ 1,23,120 crores in 2009-10 and ₹ 97,320 crores in 2010-11, it has picked up in the subsequent years. The increase over the period was 4.65 times.

During the study period, the percentage of growth over the previous year lies between -26.18 percent and 74.93 percent. The highest growth rate has been observed 74.93 percent in the year 2007-08. The negative growth rate has been observed -26.18 percent in the year 2012-13.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of an amount of FDI Equity Inflows was 16.62 percent which is a good sign of growth. During the study period of ten years, it has been observed that for six years the growth rate was above the CAGR and for three years the growth rate was below the compound annual growth rate.

Further the table envisages that the growth rate of exports made in India during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The amount of total exports has increased from ₹ 5,71,779 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 19,05,011 crores in 2013-14. The amounts of exports, then decreased to ₹ 18,96,445 crores in 2014-15 and then ₹ 17,16,378 crores in 2015-16. The increase over the period was 3 times.

During the study period, the percentage of growth over the previous year lies between -9.49 percent and 35.17 percent. The highest growth rate has been observed 35.17 percent in the year 2010-11. Whereas the negative growth rate has been registered -9.49 percent in the year 2015-16.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of exports made in India was 11.62 percent which is an encouraging sign.

2. Inflow of Foreign Direct Investment and Gross Domestic Product

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) refers to the total value of all final goods and services produced within a country in a given period of time. It is often considered an indicator of growth and standard of living for a country. Current Prices measures GDP using the current price level. Therefore, when making comparisons it shows nominal changes in GDP. Foreign Direct Investment has a close relationship with Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in India. The year-wise amount of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) equity inflows along with GDPs secured by India are seen in Table 2.

TABLE 2
YEAR-WISE AMOUNT OF FDI EQUITY INFLOWS AND GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT (GDP) IN INDIA

Years	FDI Equity Inflows (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (%)	GDP at Current Prices (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (%)
2006-07	56,390	-	39,53,276	-
2007-08	98,642	74.93	45,82,086	15.91
2008-09	1,42,829	44.80	53,03,567	15.75
2009-10	1,23,120	-13.80	61,08,903	15.18
2010-11	97,320	-20.96	72,48,860	18.66
2011-12	1,65,146	69.69	83,91,691	15.77
2012-13	1,21,907	-26.18	93,88,876	11.88
2013-14	1,47,518	21.01	104,72,807	11.54
2014-15	1,89,107	28.19	112,26,849	7.20
2015-16	2,62,322	38.72	120,80,090	7.60
CAGR (%)	16.62	-	11.82	-

Source: Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion & Reserve Bank of India.

Table 2 show the growth rate of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Equity Inflows during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The total amount of FDI Equity Inflows has increased from ₹ 56,390 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 1,42,829 crores in 2008-09. Even though the amount of FDI equity inflows declined to ₹ 1,23,120 crores in 2009-10 and ₹ 97,320 crores in 2010-11, it has picked up in the subsequent years. The increase over the period was 4.65 times.

During the study period, the percentage of growth over the previous year lies between -26.18 percent and 74.93 percent. The highest growth rate has been observed 74.93 percent in the year 2007-08. The negative growth rate has been observed -26.18 percent in the year 2012-13.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of an amount of FDI Equity Inflows was 16.62 percent which is a good sign of growth. During the study period of ten years, it has been observed that for six years the growth rate was above the CAGR and for three years the growth rate was below the compound annual growth rate.

Further the table exhibits the growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices in India during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The amount Gross Domestic Product has increased from ₹ 39,53,276 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 120,80,090 crores in 2015-16. The increase over the period was 3.05 times.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of GDP at current prices in India was 11.82 percent which is an encouraging sign.

3. Inflow of Foreign Direct Investment and Foreign Exchange Reserves

Foreign Exchange Reserves (also called as Forex Reserves) is money or other assets held by the Reserve Bank of India (Central Bank) or other monetary authorities so that it can pay if need be, its liabilities, such as the currency issued by the central bank, as well as the various bank reserves deposited with the central bank by the government and other financial institutions. The year wise amount of FDI Equity Inflows along with the Foreign Exchange Reserves of the country is furnished in Table 3.

TABLE 3
YEAR-WISE AMOUNT OF FDI EQUITY INFLOWS AND FOREIGN EXCHANGE RESERVES IN INDIA

Years	FDI Equity Inflows (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (%)	Foreign Exchange Reserves (₹ in Crores)	Annual Growth Rate (%)
2006-07	56,390	-	8,68,222	-
2007-08	98,642	74.93	12,37,965	42.59
2008-09	1,42,829	44.80	12,83,865	3.71
2009-10	1,23,120	-13.80	12,59,665	-1.88
2010-11	97,320	-20.96	13,61,013	8.05
2011-12	1,65,146	69.69	15,06,130	10.66
2012-13	1,21,907	-26.18	15,88,420	5.46
2013-14	1,47,518	21.01	18,28,380	15.11
2014-15	1,89,107	28.19	21,37,647	16.91
2015-16	2,62,322	38.72	23,75,970	11.15
CAGR (%)	-	16.62	-	10.59

Source: Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion & Reserve Bank of India.

Table 3 reveal the growth rate of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Equity Inflows during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The total amount of FDI Equity Inflows has increased from ₹ 56,390 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 1,42,829 crores in 2008-09. Even though the amount of FDI equity inflows declined to ₹ 1,23,120 crores in 2009-10 and ₹ 97,320 crores in 2010-11, it has picked up in the subsequent years. The increase over the period was 4.65 times.

During the study period, the percentage of growth over the previous year lies between -26.18 percent and 74.93 percent. The highest growth rate has been observed 74.93 percent in the year 2007-08. The negative growth rate has been observed -26.18 percent in the year 2012-13.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of an amount of FDI Equity Inflows was 16.62 percent which is a good sign of growth. During the study period of ten years, it has been observed that for six years the

growth rate was above the CAGR and for three years the growth rate was below the compound annual growth rate.

Further the table exhibits the growth rate of Foreign Exchange Earnings (FEE) in India during the period from 2006-07 to 2015-16. The amount Foreign Exchange Earnings have increased from ₹ 8,68,222 crores in 2006-07 to ₹ 12,83,865 crores in 2008-09. Even though the amount of Foreign Exchange Earnings declined to ₹ 12,59,665 crores in 2009-10, it has picked up in the subsequent years up to 2015-16. The increase over the period was 2.73 times.

During the study period, the percentage of growth over the previous year lies between -1.88 percent and 42.59 percent. The highest growth rate has been observed 42.59 percent in the year 2007-08. The negative growth rate has been observed -1.88 percent in the year 2009-10.

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of Foreign Exchange Earnings in India was 10.59 percent which is a hopeful sign.

4. Correlation

To find the relationship between the variables of Foreign Direct Investment, Exports, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Foreign Exchange Earnings (FEE) the correlation analysis is performed.

TABLE 4
CORRELATION

		FDI Inflows	Exports	Gross Domestic Product	Foreign Exchange Reserves
FDI Inflows	Pearson Correlation	1	.692*	.811**	.911**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.027	.004	.000
	N	10	10	10	10
Exports	Pearson Correlation	.692*	1	.967**	.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.027		.000	.001
	N	10	10	10	10
Gross Domestic Product	Pearson Correlation	.811**	.967**	1	.952**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	.000		.000
	N	10	10	10	10
Foreign Exchange Reserves	Pearson Correlation	.911**	.872**	.952**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.000	
	N	10	10	10	10

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 exhibits the correlation between the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Equity inflows, Exports, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices and Foreign Exchange Earnings.

Correlation between Foreign Direct Investment and exports is 0.692 which is significant at 0.05 levels. It indicates that as the FDI Equity inflows of the country increases the export also increases.

Correlation between Foreign Direct Investment and Gross Domestic Product is 0.811 which is significant at 0.01 levels. It indicates that as the FDI Equity inflows of the country increases the Gross Domestic Product also increases.

Correlation value between Foreign Direct Investment and Foreign Exchange Earnings is 0.911 which is significant at 0.01 levels. It indicates that as the FDI equity inflows of the country increases the foreign exchange reserve also increases.

VII. FINDINGS

Major findings of the study are as follows,

- It is found that the compound annual growth rate of foreign direct investment is 16.62 percent which is an encouraging trend.
- The performance with regard to the development of flow of foreign direct investment was better, except the years 2009-10, 2010-11 and 2012-13.
- It is seen from the analysis, compound annual growth rate of export made by the country was 11.62 percent which is also a welcome trend.
- FDI inflow has a positive relationship with exports made by the country.
- It is noted that the compound annual growth rate of GDP of the country was 11.82 percent which is an encouraging sign.
- It is observed that the trend of GDP was better because of the steady increase in the Gross Domestic Product during the study period.
- FDI inflow has a positive impact on Gross Domestic Product at current prices.
- It is revealed that the Compound Annual Growth Rate of Foreign Exchange Reserves was 10.59 percent, which is also a good sign. The increase over the period of the foreign exchange reserve was 2.73 times.
- FDI inflow has a close relationship with the increasing amount of foreign exchange reserves of the country.

VIII. SUGGESTIONS

- ✓ The Government of India should attract more volume of Foreign Direct Investment which in turn would help the Indian market as it is booming and has plenty of opportunities for growth.
- ✓ Better innovative marketing techniques should be adopted to attract the more Investment in India.
- ✓ The Foreign Direct Investment is largely untapped potential rural markets of India are expected to increase, compared with the current investment situation. If the foreign companies concentrate more on rural markets, the economy will grow in the future.
- ✓ The country should be ready to grab any opportunity to its fullest potential by developing in all dimensions and make it an attractive destination for Investment.
- ✓ The Government and Policy makers should make sure a stable, transparent and non-discriminatory regulatory system in the country which is the best way to attract a large amount of Foreign Direct Investment.

IX. CONCLUSION

Positive growth effects of FDI cannot be taken for granted. The ambiguous, and sometimes contradictory, empirical findings indicate that FDI must no longer be considered to be a homogeneous and universally applicable phenomenon in order to improve our understanding of the growth impact of FDI. In the ultimate analysis, it all depends on time-varying and location-specific factors, whether FDI and growth are positively correlated or not. For instance, opening up early to FDI inflows, combined with close integration into

world trade, seems to have strengthened the FDI /growth nexus. The good news for small and less advanced economies is that they can benefit from positive growth effects of FDI as much as larger and more advanced developing countries.

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